

TEACHING ENGLISH USING VARIOUS MULTIMEDIA AND DIGITAL TECHNICAL EQUIPMENT

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The development of information technologies in the field of education has formed a new trend, within which the active use of multimedia technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages is perceived as a necessary requirement of the time. However, the scope of the term “multimedia technologies” is used in various studies, depending on the research tasks and subject area of the study, quite flexibly. Therefore, we limit the content of this term to the following definition. Multimedia, in relation to the process of teaching a foreign language, means the integration of several media elements (audio, video, graphics, text, animation, etc.) into one synergistic and symbiotic whole, which creates additional effects for the student in the perception of information. Multimedia technology, in turn, is software used to create and run multimedia projects in which information is presented digitally using various media elements. And here we should not forget that each software has its own advantages and disadvantages due to the fact that the software is focused on solving various cognitive tasks, differentially affects the channels of information perception, and the ability to form cognitive skills. Therefore, the passion of the pedagogical community for the idea of digitalization of the educational process, and, as a consequence, the introduction of multimedia technologies into the learning process, should be limited to a clear understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of multimedia when solving problems of developing professional and general cultural competencies of future specialists.

The introduction of multimedia technologies into the practice of teaching a foreign language is possible in two directions. The first involves the use of multimedia as “supporting” means in the system of traditional teaching methods. The second direction is related to the creation of a foreign language course, which, as a rule, is developed on digital platforms that make it possible to comprehensively solve the problems of methodological support of the taught discipline. Examples of this approach can be developments based on gamification technologies [1], linear and non-linear presentations, chat platforms, blogging, mobile applications, etc.

However, we should not forget that the effectiveness of using multimedia in education is conditional and depends on many conditions, starting from the concept of pedagogical design of the course, ending with the quality of its visual content. Therefore, there is no unambiguous assessment of the level of effectiveness of multimedia in the process of teaching foreign languages.

Positive assessments of the use of multimedia in teaching foreign languages are associated with solving the problem of motivating students to learn a foreign language. Proponents of this assessment emphasize the fact that in classroom conditions, the teacher is deprived of the opportunity to have an individual approach to the student [3]. This situation demotivates the student and reduces his interest in learning a foreign language.

The second aspect is related to solving problems to stimulate cognitive processes in students. In particular, we are talking about adapting the methodology of teaching a foreign language course to the perception patterns of the digital generation: the dominance of clip thinking, high requirements for the level of information visualization, a low level of concentration and analytical skills, and the skill of quickly switching between different types of activities.

In the context of solving these problems, it is assumed that multimedia technologies have high potential in solving the above problems. For example, presentation software allows you to create a foreign language course with active visual content, with maximum focus on video; gamification of the educational process solves problems associated with individualizing the trajectory of language training, with motivation to learn a foreign language, developing skills in project work and group interaction; mobile applications intensify the process of language training; All types of pedagogical chats (free topic chat, collaborative task-oriented chat, practice chat etc.) allow not only to optimize the process of monitoring learning outcomes, but also to “immerse” students in a language environment with native speakers. Therefore, the potential of multimedia in the process of managing the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language directly depends on the technology in which the course is implemented.

Issues of the utilitarian value of multimedia technologies are discussed separately [2]. A positive aspect here is the ability of this type of technology to reduce costs associated with storing and transmitting large amounts of information, and implementing distance learning and communications. But a positive assessment of the capabilities of multimedia technologies is significantly offset by the difficulties of their implementation. We should not forget that the effectiveness of multimedia in the learning process depends on

the level of their interactivity, however, the technical capabilities of universities do not always allow the full creation of an interactive multimedia environment. It is also important that the introduction of multimedia technologies into the learning process creates additional burden for a teacher who does not belong to the generation of digital natives and is often conservative in the perception of technological innovations. Therefore, a significant range of issues related to the preparation of the course creates difficulties and requires significant effort to transform the subjective cognitive abilities of the teacher and the principles of working with information.

Summarizing the study of the possible effects of using multimedia technologies in teaching a foreign language, it should be noted that there is an antinomy in assessments of the effectiveness of these technologies. A positive assessment of the use of multimedia is based on constructive changes in students' motivation to learn a foreign language. Individualization of the learning process and adaptation of the course content to the peculiarities of perception of "digital natives" allow the teacher to more actively interact with the student, involving them in the process of learning a foreign language. Multimedia not only allows you to work with educational content in a convenient way, but also reduces the level of stress and anxiety during learning. Another aspect of positive assessments of the effectiveness of multimedia is associated with the possibilities of introducing project-based approaches to language learning, which are accompanied by the activation and development of social interaction processes in student groups. This organization of learning allows students to go beyond the classroom and provides language practice in a natural environment.

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